

The Infinity Paradigm: Demonstrating the Realness of Infinity as a Mathematical Entity.

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Abstract-

Infinity has been a puzzling concept throughout the history of mathematical and physical evolution. The notion of boundlessness or limitlessness has captivated the human imagination for centuries. From the ancient Greeks to modern-day mathematicians, the concept of infinity has been the subject of extensive investigation and debate. In this article, we will explore the reality of infinity in the mathematical and physical realms, shedding light on its significance and the way it shapes our understanding of reality.

Introduction-

In the realm of mathematics, the concept of infinity stands as an enigmatic and fascinating idea that has captivated human intellect for centuries. It challenges our understanding of numbers, continuity, and the very nature of reality itself. Despite its ethereal nature, there is a compelling case to assert that infinity is not merely a theoretical abstraction but a bona fide entity within the real number system. This discourse delves into the heart of this intriguing proposition, aiming to unravel the mathematical intricacies that support the existence of infinity as a genuine member of the real number line. Through a journey spanning ancient philosophical debates, historical mathematical breakthroughs, and modern formalisations, we endeavour to shed light on the tangible attributes that render infinity as more than just a conceptual construct. By examining its role in calculus, set theory, and even the empirical world, we strive to unveil the profound implications of acknowledging infinity's realness, ultimately reshaping our perception of number theory and the very fabric of mathematical reality.

Keywords

Infinite.

Calculation-

We all know that $\lim_{x \rightarrow \pi/2} \tan(x)$ almost approaches infinity and various other functions have infinite value.

However, infinity has a definite value, no matter how large.

Let's suppose

$\lim_{x \rightarrow \pi/2} \tan(x)$ approaches infinity

In-order to find out whether infinity is a real or imaginary number we will refer to the definition of real numbers i.e. if a number is real it will be its own complex conjugate.

Lets suppose infinity is a complex number which is given by ket vector A

$$\infty = x+iy = |A\rangle \text{-----} \text{(equation 1)}$$

Where $|x| = \infty$, $i^2 = -1$, y is any real number, where $|A\rangle = \text{ket vector A}$, so

$x+iy = \infty$ adding x to iy will always give infinity because iy is always negligible compared to infinity----- (statement 1)

$1/0 = \infty$ or not defined (as per English terms)

So

$$x+iy = \frac{1}{0} + iy$$

$$= \frac{1 + iy \cdot 0}{0}$$

$$= \frac{1}{0} \text{ (Hence proved the statement 1)}$$

Upon complex conjugating equation 1

$\langle A | = x-iy$ is again infinity because x is ∞ so if we subtract iy from infinity we will get infinity. ——— (statement 2)

Where $\langle A |$ is bra vector A

So

$$x-iy = \frac{1}{0} - iy$$

$$= \frac{1 - iy \cdot 0}{0}$$

$$= \frac{1}{0} \text{ (Hence proved the statement 2)}$$

So we have come to the conclusion that $|A\rangle = \langle A |$

Any number which is its own complex conjugate is a real number.

Also you can see the imaginary part iy on doing mathematical functions becomes zero hence not defined or ∞ is a part of real number system.

Discussion-

In Actions, Processes, Objects and Schemas theory attempts to understand infinity have been made by Weller et al (1). Infinity has been an obstruction in understanding space-time singularities inside blackhole and also the beginning of the universe. This article attempts to explain the meaning of infinity and will have implications in physical universe.

Refferances-

- 1) Weller, Kirk & Brown, Anne & ed, ed & Mcdonald, Michael & Stenger, Cindy. (2004). Intimations of infinity. Notices of the American Mathematical Society. 51.

Conflict of interest-

The authors have nothing to declare.